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MODERN PROBLEMS OF EDUCATION: ANALYSIS OF THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING A HYBRID LEARNING

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Abstract: *The article discusses the possibilities and prospects for the use of mixed and hybrid educational technologies in vocational education institutions. Blended and hybrid learning models and the possibilities of their integration into the educational process are explored. A typology of teaching models is proposed, possible combinations of these models are characterized and their didactic potential is analyzed. Examples of the implementation of hybrid educational technologies are demonstrated and proposals are formulated for their improvement and development.*

Keywords: *education; hybrid technology; blended learning; hybrid learning; e-learning; interactive training.*

INTRODUCTION

An important factor of progress in any sphere of society is the effectiveness of the use of modern means of information and communication technologies. Along with the development of the economy, medicine, and politics, the education system is also being modernized, to which society's demand for the use of new technologies is being fully directed, bringing it to a higher level of development.

A significant trend in improving the modern education system is the search for innovative approaches to make learning more dynamic and relevant to the needs of its recipients. Currently, so-called e-learning systems are actively developing, based on the primary use of modern information and communication technologies.

UNESCO experts gave the following definition of e-learning - this is learning using the Internet and multimedia [1]. A.V. Loginova in publication [2] analyzes the development of these systems and characterizes the problems caused by such training. B. Tomlinson and K. Whittaker in the manual "Blended learning in English language teaching: course development and implementation" [3] proposed a four-element classification of e-learning systems:

- 1) Blended learning (up to 45% online learning).
- 2) Hybrid learning (40-80% online learning).
- 3) Distance learning (more than 80% online learning).
- 4) Training via the Internet (minimum online training).

A number of authors make attempts to contrast e-learning with traditional (face to face with a teacher) [4, 5].

In our opinion, such a opposition is not correct and justified, since these are completely different forms of education, with their own advantages and disadvantages, but complement each other. For example, students' work with a teacher in the classroom (practical part) is supplemented by remote learning of lecture material (theoretical part). Practice shows that the greatest effect is achieved in a combination of these two types of training. The concept of blended learning seems much more constructive and expedient learning), which involves a combination of traditional teaching methods in the classroom (Face-To-Face Learning) with online training (Online learning). In particular, K.J. Bonka and C.R. Graham in 2006 in the book Handbook of Blended Learning " defined blended learning as a form of learning that combines traditional learning through personal communication (face-to-face, Face-To-Face) with learning through the use of computer technology. In our opinion, one of the main advantages of the concept of blended learning is the use of educational technologies that are different in nature, ensuring a synergistic effect.

Along with the concept of "blended learning" you can find the term "hybrid learning" (eng. hybrid learning). At first glance, these two terms seem synonymous, but they are not. Blended learning focuses on the required combination of traditional human-centered and online learning, while hybrid learning is about finding the right combination of educational technologies, whether delivered online or offline.

Research methods

When implementing hybrid educational technologies, most of the course is taught online. Unlike blended learning, the hybrid learning scenario involves the student's primary interaction with an online educational resource, while communication with the teacher largely performs an advisory or auxiliary function.

Hybrid learning technology involves unique management of the student's time while providing him with methodological support, in particular, through:

- 1) synchronous training, similar to an online class, which can be carried out on the basis of individual training;
- 2) asynchronous learning, which provides an ideal platform for the implementation of distance learning.

Hybrid learning is characterized by four properties that distinguish it favorably from other educational technologies:

- 1) a combination of collective training and individual training;
- 2) a combination of synchronous learning and asynchronous learning;
- 3) a combination of independent and group learning;
- 4) a combination of formal and informal learning from the point of view of its implementation throughout life (English Lifetime learning).

In our opinion, the most important advantages of blended learning include:

- increasing student motivation;
- independence in preparing students to participate in the educational process;
- flexibility of the educational process;
- convenient monitoring of student progress;
- the ability to choose a convenient study schedule; - reduction of training costs;
- obtaining a synergistic effect through the use of educational technologies that are different in nature.

Formulation of the problem

But it should also be noted that , like any educational technology, blended learning has a number of limitations:

- students must have basic competencies in the field of information and communication technologies, as well as high motivation to learn;
- the information and educational environment of many universities is not ready to support blended learning technology;
- lack of a sufficient number of highly qualified IT specialists to solve various and extraordinary problems of informatization of educational activities of the university;
- the unpreparedness of many teachers to implement and use blended learning technology, including due to a lack of understanding of its prospects and reluctance to master new educational technologies;
- insufficient provision of online learning with relevant educational and methodological materials.

These are problems that require a specific solution.

Solution

The innovation and promise of using mixed and hybrid educational technologies in the educational process is due to the undoubted synergistic effect of the mutual complementarity of traditional and online forms and means of education, which are different in nature. However, the range of technologies already used or promising for use in the educational process is not limited to those mentioned above. Systematizing and characterizing technologies have been proposed, various combinations of which are promising, in our opinion, for the implementation of multi-component hybrid educational systems.

1. Face to Face (FtF) is a traditional educational technology consisting of the direct transfer of knowledge and skills from teacher to student;

2. Face to Book (FtB) is a traditional educational technology based on independent acquisition of knowledge from published paper sources;
3. Face to Ebook (FtEb) is an educational technology that provides for independent acquisition of knowledge from electronic sources;
4. Computer Learning (CL) is an educational technology that provides for the implementation of the educational process exclusively using information and communication technologies, i.e. without the participation of a teacher;
5. Online Learning (OnL) is a variant of CL technology that provides for the implementation of the entire educational process or its specific stages in real time, i.e. online. Synonymous with the term “ Online” Learning " is considered the term "Synchronous learning" [13];
6. Offline Learning (OfL) is a version of CL technology that provides for the implementation of the entire educational process or its specific stages online. Synonymous with the term " Offline" Learning " is considered the term "Asynchronous learning" [13];
7. Face to Equipment (FtEq) - obtaining skills and abilities to work on real equipment or in direct contact with real objects of activity;
8. Face to Equipment Model (FtEqM) - obtaining skills and abilities to work on full-scale (physical) models of real equipment or real objects of activity;
9. Face to Computer Model (FtCM) - obtaining skills and abilities to work on computer models (simulators) of real equipment or real objects of activity;
10. Face to Virtual Reality (FtVR) – gaining skills and abilities to work in the virtual reality space [7];
11. Face to Augmented Reality (FtAR) – obtaining skills and abilities to work in the augmented reality space [6].

Research results

Analysis of the above list allows us to assert that the vast majority of educational systems (and not just mixed ones) have a multi-component hybrid nature. For example, when studying web technologies at TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi of the Fergana Branch, teachers provide students with lecture notes in electronic form (in “ Word ” format) or in the form of a presentation (in “ PowerPoint ” format) to effectively master the discipline, i.e. .e. elements of FtEb technology are being implemented . During practical classes, in the process of direct communication with the teacher (FtF), the most important and interesting topics of the course are analyzed, control tasks or problems that cause difficulties are solved. The university has also created a library where lecture courses and recommended literature are located, which allows us to talk about the implementation of elements of the FtB technology . OnL and OfL tools are available , such as chats, forums, e- mail , Skype , with the help of which remote communication between teachers and students is carried out.

The results of the study showed that the application of this method was more effective in obtaining and understanding a new topic. The average score of students in group 634-20 studying in the traditional format at the first intermediate was 65 points. After using the hybrid learning format, students in the same

group had an average score of 74 points. From this analysis it follows that the hybrid format of education is the most effective and is recommended for implementation in all universities of Uzbekistan.

Universities of Uzbekistan, as a result of the implementation of the 2017 project “Universities as centers of space for creating innovation,” began to actively introduce virtual and augmented reality technologies into the educational process. Thus, the educational program “Augmented and Virtual Reality Technologies in Printed Products”, with the help of FtF , FtB and FtEb technologies, provides students with the opportunity to get acquainted with the development of virtual (FtVR) and augmented (FtAR) reality applications , allows them to gain skills in working with the necessary hardware and software complexes. Students learn to create interactive applications for mobile devices and printed materials.

However, the possibilities of combining modern educational technologies are far from being fully realized in practice. We will offer several promising, in our opinion, combinations of educational technologies, the implementation of which for the relevant areas of training or specific disciplines could bring a significant educational effect.

At the Department of Foreign Languages, a noticeable effect can be obtained by combining Face components to Virtual Reality , Online Learning , Computer Learning , Face to Face and Face to Ebook . Classes would be conducted in the form of video/ audio lectures , video lessons, PowerPoint presentations prepared by the teacher. They could take place both at the university and outside it (at home). To effectively learn a foreign language, it would be necessary to use a virtual interlocutor, for example, using VR applications. With their help, the student is “transported” to a virtual environment, where he can interact with virtual characters using speech recognition technology. Examples of such applications are the software systems MondlyVR and MyET . We also note that the systematic use of tools for assessing learning outcomes implemented in these software products will significantly increase the objectivity of monitoring educational achievements.

Conclusion

In our opinion, the joint use of educational technologies that are different in nature in the educational process can bring a significant synergistic effect. The sources of this effect are, first of all, a more complete and targeted use of the educational potential of specific didactic means, as well as increasing the motivation of students to use innovative technologies and the possibility of constructing and implementing individual educational trajectories. At the same time, the creation of such multi-component educational environments, heterogeneous in structure and hybrid in content, is associated with certain difficulties due to the need for significant financial costs, the insufficient development of the infrastructure of educational organizations, as well as the conservatism and insufficient preparedness of many teachers to use innovative forms of organizing educational process. However, the development of society cannot be stopped, and the creation of multi-component educational environments is one of the strategic directions for modernizing the educational system as a whole.

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